

References

- [1] F. Amini, N. H. Riche, B. Lee, J. Leboe-McGowan, and P. Irani, “Hooked on data videos: Assessing the effect of animation and pictographs on viewer engagement,” in *Proceedings of the 2018 International Conference on Advanced Visual Interfaces*, ser. AVI '18. New York, NY, USA: Association for Computing Machinery, 2018. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1145/3206505.3206552>
- [2] B. Bach, C. Shi, N. Heulot, T. Madhyastha, T. Grabowski, and P. Dragicevic, “Time curves: Folding time to visualize patterns of temporal evolution in data,” *IEEE Transactions on Visualization and Computer Graphics*, vol. 22, no. 1, pp. 559–568, 2016.
- [3] B. Bach, N. Henry Riche, S. Carpendale, and H. Pfister, “The emerging genre of data comics,” *IEEE Computer Graphics and Applications*, vol. 38, pp. 6–13, 05 2017.
- [4] A. Beheshti, A. Tabebordbar, and B. Benatallah, “istory: Intelligent storytelling with social data,” 04 2020, pp. 253–256.
- [5] F. Bosello, C. Colli, P. Clini, I. Dražić, D. Dražina, A. Pugliese, R. Quattrini, and G. Vettorel, “Remember: an adriatic network of virtual museums to highlight ports culture, traditions and history,” *IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering*, vol. 949, p. 012082, 11 2020.
- [6] R. Brumana, D. Oreni, S. Caspani, and M. Previtali, “Virtual museums and built environment: Narratives and immersive experience via multi-temporal geodata hub,” *Virtual Archaeology Review*, vol. 9, p. 34, 07 2018.
- [7] A. S. Chaudhary and A. Arora, “Storytelling data visualization for grievances management system,” in *Futuristic Trends in Networks and Computing Technologies*, P. K. Singh, S. Sood, Y. Kumar, M. Paprzycki, A. Pljonkin, and W.-C. Hong, Eds. Singapore: Springer Singapore, 2020, pp. 395–405.
- [8] S. Concannon, N. Rajan, P. Shah, D. Smith, M. Ursu, and J. Hook, “Brooke leave home: Designing a personalized film to support public engagement with open data,” in *Proceedings of the 2020 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*, ser. CHI '20. New York, NY, USA: Association for Computing Machinery, 2020, p. 1–14. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1145/3313831.3376462>
- [9] V. Echeverria, R. Martinez-Maldonado, and S. Buckingham Shum, “Towards data storytelling to support teaching and learning,” in *Proceedings of the 29th Australian Conference on Computer-Human Interaction*, ser. OZCHI '17. New York, NY, USA: Association for Computing Machinery, 2017, p. 347–351. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1145/3152771.3156134>

- [10] V. Echeverria, R. Martinez-Maldonado, R. Granda, K. Chiluita, C. Conati, and S. Buckingham Shum, “Driving data storytelling from learning design,” 03 2018, pp. 131–140.
- [11] S. Ketchell, W. Chinthammit, and U. Engelke, “Situated storytelling with slam enabled augmented reality,” in *Proceedings of the 17th International Conference on Virtual-Reality Continuum and Its Applications in Industry*, ser. VRCAI '19. New York, NY, USA: Association for Computing Machinery, 2019. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1145/3359997.3365681>
- [12] Z. Koukopoulos and D. Koukopoulos, “A participatory digital platform for cultural heritage within smart city environments,” 01 2016, pp. 412–419.
- [13] J. Liem, C. Perin, and J. Wood, “Structure and empathy in visual data storytelling: Evaluating their influence on attitude,” *Computer Graphics Forum*, vol. 39, 06 2020.
- [14] Y. Loukissas, *All Data Are Local: Thinking Critically in a Data-Driven Society*, 01 2019.
- [15] A. Lunterova, O. Spetko, and G. Palamas, *Explorative Visualization of Food Data to Raise Awareness of Nutritional Value*, 08 2019, pp. 180–191.
- [16] O. Philbin-Briscoe, B. Simon, S. Mudur, C. Poullis, S. Rizvić, D. Boskovic, F. Liarokapis, I. Katsouri, S. Demesticha, and D. Skarlatos, “A serious game for understanding ancient seafaring in the mediterranean sea,” 09 2017.
- [17] S. Podworny, Y. Fleischer, S. Hüsing, R. Biehler, D. Frischmeier, L. Höper, and C. Schulte, “Using data cards for teaching data based decision trees in middle school,” 10 2021.
- [18] H. Saksono and A. G. Parker, “Reflective informatics through family storytelling: Self-discovering physical activity predictors,” in *Proceedings of the 2017 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*, ser. CHI '17. New York, NY, USA: Association for Computing Machinery, 2017, p. 5232–5244. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1145/3025453.3025651>
- [19] D. Seyser and M. Zeiller, “Scrollytelling – an analysis of visual storytelling in online journalism,” 07 2018, pp. 401–406.
- [20] L. Stenliden, U. Bodén, and J. Nissen, “Students as producers of interactive data visualizations—digitally skilled to make their voices heard,” *Journal of Research on Technology in Education*, vol. 51, pp. 1–17, 02 2019.
- [21] Z. Wang, H. Dingwall, and B. Bach, “Teaching data visualization and storytelling with data comic workshops,” in *Extended Abstracts of the 2019 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*, ser. CHI EA '19. New York, NY, USA: Association for Computing Machinery, 2019, p. 1–9. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1145/3290607.3299043>

- [22] M. Wilkerson, W. Finzer, T. Erickson, and D. Hernandez, “Reflective data storytelling for youth: The codap story builder,” in *Interaction Design and Children*, ser. IDC '21. New York, NY, USA: Association for Computing Machinery, 2021, p. 503–507. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1145/3459990.3465177>
- [23] W. Zeng, A. Dong, X. Chen, and Z.-l. Cheng, “Vistory: interactive story-board for exploring visual information in scientific publications,” *Journal of Visualization*, vol. 24, 08 2020.
- [24] Y. Zhang and A. Lugmayr, “Designing a user-centered interactive data-storytelling framework,” in *Proceedings of the 31st Australian Conference on Human-Computer-Interaction*, ser. OZCHI'19. New York, NY, USA: Association for Computing Machinery, 2020, p. 428–432. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1145/3369457.3369507>